

Lexicon Variations on Traditional Weaving

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ABSTRACT: The research entitled Lexicon Variation on Traditional Weaving is a qualitative research focusses on the analysis of the semantic function of the lexicon process. The focus of the analysis is formulated on two problems (1) types of lexicons weaving and (2) function and meaning of lexicon weaving. Observation and interview methods are applied for the data collection. Observation method is realized with interviewing the weavers when they do weave activity in the workshop. At the same time the owner of the weaving industry who is as the key informant is also interviewed. Unstructured deep interviewed was done for several weavers and the key informants. Theories on semantics from Leech (1981) and Lobner (2013) are applied for analysing the function and meaning of lexicons found in traditional weaving. It was found 100 of lexicons which were classified into 3 types. The dominant number of lexicons belong to the lexicon equipment which is followed apparently by lexicons for material and lexicons process. The semantic function of the lexicons in accordance with its classification is dominated by the lexicon process.

KEYWORDS: functions, lexicon, type, meaning, weaving.

1. INTRODUCTION

Lexicon (lexicon, vocabulary) can be interpreted (1) as the component of language that contains all information about meaning and the use of word in language; (2) the richness of words a person or a speaker has, a writer or even a language; vocabulary; (3) a list of words arranged like dictionary, but with a brief and practical explanation (Kridalaksana, 1982: 98). Semantics is a branch of knowledge of linguistics. Analysis on semantics for every utterance containing several lexicons is mandatory to find function and meaning of every lexicon. Verhaar (2006:13) states that semantics discuss meaning and significance.

Classification lexicon reviewed from the meaning is very diverse, for example meaning lexicon on plants, food, ceremonies, etc. Classification lexicon on traditional weaving is the focus in the research. Weaving is one of Asian nations culture including Indonesia, especially Bali. Traditional weaving activities use a lot of varied lexicon which need to be classified and documented for the sake of language preservation. This research applied semantic theory (lexical semantics) especially the semantics function for analyzing the data. Kridalaksana (2009: 69) states semantics function is the role element in a speech and its relationship in a way it is structured with other elements, especially in the field of meaning. This research analyzes the function of meaning of vocabulary in traditional weaving based on the vocabulary function mentioned in the two research locations. Semantics function referred to meaning lexical in accordance with the reference because of the existing elements in a language, out of its use or the context (Kridalaksana 2009: 149).

Previous similar research conducted by Sukarini and Beratha in 2023 shows there are lots of lexicon used in traditional weaving activity like lexicons equipment, lexicon materials, lexicon motifs, lexicon colors, lexicon process, and lexicon post- processes. Based on the phenomenon, research needs to be conducted emphasizing about types of lexicons used in the domain of traditional weaving. The focus of this research is on the classification and semantics function on lexicon on traditional weaving for the sake of documenting diverse type of lexicon as well as analyzing the semantics function of the lexicons.

2. THEORY AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Lobner (2013: 1) states that linguistic semantics is a field of linguistics only regarding with expression meaning whether it's words, phrases, grammatical forms, and sentences, not associated meaning with an action or phenomenon. Leech (1981) classified 7 types of meaning in which one of the seven types of meaning is the conceptual or denotative meaning. The meaning of conceptual or denotative meaning is namely meaning indeed from a word in which the meaning is not influenced by context of situation. Based on the theory of meaning from Lobner and Leech the research data is analyzed using the semantic theory from

both experts. Lobner 's semantic theory is for determining the lexicon classification on traditional weaving and Leech semantics theory for analysing the meaning of semantics function.

There are 4 similar previous research that have been reviewed and provided significant contribution to this research. This literary study did some research on vocabulary and semantics functions used in (1) Ethnobotany Malay Sukadana, (2) Fishermen Devices Tools, and (3) Traditional Banjar House Ornaments. Jupitasari, et al (2014) with the research title Semantics Function on Ethnobotany Malay Sukadana Vocabulary. Jupitasari's research focuses on semantics function on ethnobotany vocabulary specifically the utilization plant of medicine in Malay Sukadana Society in four villages namely Benawai Agung Village, Sutera Village, Pangkalan Buton Village, and Harapan Mulia Village in the Sukadana District. Jupitasari et al. applied method of descriptive qualitative. Source of data using the vocabulary of plant drugs Malay Sukadana as spoken by the language speaker who are at once as the informant at the same time. Research results show that there are several vocabulary plants that also has another name that refers to the same meaning so that matter enrich ethnobotany vocabulary of Malay Sukadana. Research done by Lontoh (2018) with the title Semantics Function of Fishing Tools Vocabulary and Techniques of Fishermen in the Manado Boulevard Area. Aims of this research (1) to identify vocabulary and equipment of fishermen community, and (2) describe as well as analyze semantics function of vocabulary equipment and techniques fishing fisherman community especially in the Manado Boulevard Area. The use of observation method and interview with the prioritize that the researcher as the main instrument. Research results show that was found as many as 30 vocabulary fish catcher tools and 14 vocabularies on technique of catching fish. Data analysis is classified from vocabulary, phonetics, and semantics lexical functions. There are several similar vocabulary with different semantics function and on the other hand there is the use of the same catching tool however with different function so that there are different vocabularies. Research done by Hestiyana (2020) entitled Classification of Lexicon and Function of Social Values of Traditional Banjar House Ornament. This research aims to classify as well as analyze lexicon and social function on Traditional Banjar House ornament. This research uses theory of lexicon from Chaer (2007) and theory of social function value from Sprangr (2004). Data sources consist of written and oral data. The method used is observation method with interviewing technique. Research results show that lexicon on Traditional Banjar Houses ornament is classified based on building equipment completed with as many as 10 carving motifs. Sukarini and Sutjiati Beratha (2023) with their research entitled Communication Symbols on Woven Fabric *Songket*. Research results show that the motif on the cloth weaving songket is classified into five, namely figurative motifs, geometric motifs, floral motifs, fauna motifs, and decorative motifs. The meaning and ideology conveyed in the symbol's cloth weaving *songket* through its motifs has its similarity with ikat weaving, namely glorification to natural universe. Weaving activity uses relevant lexicons which need to be researched.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

Observation method accompanied with several techniques such as participated observation technique. Here the researchers participates as well as at the research location together with the informants who are doing the activity of weaving. Researchers interact with key informants along with the weaving workers. During the observations, the interview was also conducted by questioning all things seen or heard about weaving and related to the problem under study is used to obtain more complete knowledge and understanding. In observation researchers moved from one informant to another informant with varying duration times. The aspects that are observed in observation (1) the condition / situation in the informant workplace; (2) weaving workers as well as the situation including gender, age, profession, place of origin, etc.; (3) activities carried out by the weaving worker in that situation (4) objects that are in place and its function as well as the location; (5) action of weaving worker in the process of activities. Deep interview techniques were applied in this research especially the moment of digging up information as the experience of the individual referred to individual life history or human document (Koentjaraningrat, 1989: 158). Researcher delivered questions without being structured. For example, at the observation moment which involves weaving workers are currently doing their specification like *ngelos*, *nyepih*, *mempen*, etc. Assisted by 3 field workers the researcher notices every step taken and asked in a way directly to each worker about the activities carried out and the materials used. It happened questioning and answering for each specification work. Communication will move to another weaving worker if sufficient information is already obtained or before confirming to the key informant. The role of key informant is if there are things that cannot be answered by the weaving workers it was clarified by the key informant. Through deep technique interview like these two ways the communication can be flexibly in progress, the condition is more open so that more information can be obtained, conversation can

run smooth because questioning and answering are in progress as well as there is no boring situation for researcher and also for informant. Data collected in study mostly in the form of qualitative data. This qualitative data is analyzed following qualitative procedure data analysis as put forward by Miles and Huberman (1992), namely data reduction, presenting data, interpreting data, and drawing conclusions.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Types of Lexicons in Traditional Weaving

Types or classification of lexicon based on the data and information collected in the research field or research location. Lexicon in traditional weaving can be classified into 3, namely (1) lexicon on materials, (2) lexicon on equipment, and (3) lexicon for the processing of cloth weaving. The classification is described as below.

4.2.1 Lexicon on Material

To produce a sheet of weaving cloth needs several materials. Various materials have their respective lexicons. The following are lexicons of woven materials obtained at the time of research data collection in two weaving industries located in Denpasar and Semarang Cities.

The main basic material for weaving is thread. There are 2 types of thread which have important roles in weaving which are named *lusi* or *lungsi* thread (vertical thread) and *pakan* or motif thread (horizontal thread). Upright straight weaving between the two types of thread will produce cloth weaving. The vertical thread following the length of cloth and *pakan* or motif thread because of the woven pattern lies on the *pakan* thread. There are some types of thread used for weaving such as the basic thread, decoration thread, textured thread, cotton thread and this cotton thread consists of mercerized cotton thread, combed cotton thread, and carded cotton thread, silk thread, rayon thread, and nylon thread. Other material is the substance for dyeing which consisting of dye natural substance obtained from plants and their parts like root, tree's bark, wood, leaves, seeds, fruit, and flowers; and dye synthetic substances (made of chemistry) which consists of *tunjung*, direct, dion, fixanol, sodium nitrite, sulfa acid, rapid dyes substances, and pigments. There are also other materials like lime, sulfur, alum, etc. Below are pictures of some weaving materials.

Pakan or motif thread
has been tied up

Coiled Thread

Thread that

Source: research doc.

Source: research doc.

Source: research doc.

4.2.2 Lexicon on Weaving Equipment

Weaving equipment is an absolute thing for processing the woven materials which was then made into a sheet weaving cloth. Weaving equipment here is a weaving tool operated manually or without machine movement which is named *Alat Tenun Bukan Mesin* (ATBM). Weaving equipment has its own lexicons appropriately separate with its function. Here are some lexicons on weaving equipment as can be seen below like *belida*, *seleran*, *bumbungan*, *serat*, *sekoci*, *pleteng*, *tundaka*, *prorogan*, *gunun*, *gunun gede*, *gunun motif*, *injakan gunun*, *palet*, *krerek*, *por*, *pengilingan*, *penamplikan*, *jandra*, *boom*, *pengredegan*, lining, hook thread, spool, comb, meter, raffia rope, scales, stove, pot, brush, hands glove, scissors, masks, and so on. The following are pictures of weaving equipment.

penamplikan

Source: research doc.

Pengilingan

Source: research doc.

Sekoci and Palet

Source: research doc.

4.2.3 Lexicon on Weaving Process

Lexicons in the weaving process are very related to the process being carried out. Below are several lexicons used at the time the weaving workers are doing the activity of weaving. The following lexicons in weaving process among others are: *nyelub*, *nyatri* / *nyolet*, *ngelos*, *nyepih* / *ngincrin*, *nganyinin*, *ngediing*, *DII*>>> inject (*nyucuk*), *mapal*, *mepen* / *nyangka*, *nyuci*, drawing motif, *nyemuh*, *mebed*, basic color shroud, *melut*, weaving. Below are pictures of some weaving processes.

Mempen Process

Source: research doc.

Mebed Process or The Process of tying

Source: research doc.

Ngelos

Source: research doc.

4.2 Functions Semantics Lexicon Weaving

Analysis on semantics function consists of 30 lexicons process found at the time of data collection in the two research locations. The analysis is the weaving process lexicons which consists of verbs and verb phrases. Lexicons in the forms of verb and verb phrase are used in processing for the 2 types of thread, *lusi* or *lungsi* and *pakan* or motif thread. Processing cloth weaving started with several processes on both types of thread. The process for *lusi* thread consists of above 5 stages like *nyelub* 'dyeing', *ngelos* 'glazing', *mepen* 'annealing', *nyuntik* or *nyucuk* 'injecting', and finally *nenun* 'weaving'. The process for the *pakan* thread or consists of 10 stages starts *ngelos* 'glazing' and further followed with the processes such as *mepen* 'annealing', decoration, drawing motifs, *mebed* or *ngiket* 'tying', *nyelub* 'dyeing', *melut* 'releasing', *nyatri* 'dyeing the *pakan* thread', *nyepih* 'separating' *ngediing* 'further processing of *pakan* thread', and finally is weaving. The processes on *pakan* thread are many more because of the design is in this thread. Here is the analysis of some data (verbs and verb phrases) delivered in pictures and description.

Dyeing *pakan* or motif thread

Source: research doc.

Nyelub ‘dyeing’ comes from the word *celub* which means to put into some liquid. The semantic function of the word *celub* is the process of putting an object into some liquid with the result whether or not there is a change in colour. In the weaving process, *nyelub* is coloring the *pakan* thread through dyeing that matches the type of thread and the desired color. The process is done by dipping the thread into a bucket that has been filled with colored liquid after the thread is released from the weaving and wetted so that the dye can easily absorb the untied thread.

Mapal process

Source: research doc.

Mempen process

Source: research doc.

Drawing or designing

Source: research doc.

Nyatri ‘dyeing *pakan* thread’

Source: research doc.

Semantics function of lexicon *mapal* is a separation process on *pakan* thread one by one so that we can fit the activity of weaving. Weaving equipment’s needed in the *mapal* process are windmills, drums, and tools for rotating. The process is to put the end of *pakan* thread on the windmill for the easier process of separating and releasing one by one. Next process is right hand turning the drums and left hand holding the thread for the purpose of giving tension. This process is conducted repetitively until all thread moved to the drum.

Mempen is the second process in weaving cloth after the process of *ngelos* ‘glasing’ and this is the step for designing the *pakan* thread. Semantics lexicon function is to make sure the compiling of *pakan* threads with the right parameters. The process of filling or compiling the *pakan* thread in quantity, length, and width. It is made in square to be easier to do the design motif. The function of *mempen* process is very important because this process is to ensure the thread arrangement in the right track and ready to be continued for the weaving process.

The drawing process is a furthermore step after the *mempen* process. The semantic lexicon function of drawing is to prepare the motif design. The motif design is drawn on the frame since it will be much easier for the process of binding or tying. In this process there is a pattern or the print that has been designed with a certain motif design. This pattern uses basic material like cloth perforated in accordance with motif design. When the motif is designed on the cloth it will be in accordance with designs in the pattern. The semantic function of lexicon *nyatri* or *nyolet* is the process of coloring motifs on *pakan* thread by hanging or spreading out the thread that has been dyeing and releasing the ties. Equipment such as wood for *nyatri* or a brush pen that has been wrapped around with sewing thread. These tools function for putting the threads after the process of *nyatri* and the thread will be separated through the next process named *nyepih*.

The process of *nyepih*

Source: research doc

Injection process or *nyucuk*

Source: research doc

the process of *ngani*

Source: research doc

Nyepih is a separation process of thread after the process of *nyatri* which is done by using a tool made of wood for separating the threads and then continued with the process of *nyepih*. The process of *nyepih* started with putting the result of the thread through the process of *nyatri* on the wood for *nyatri*, which then the thread will be taken per piece and linked to the circles iron on the wood. The next step is to rotate the *plating* and *catri* wood simultaneously until all the *pakan* thread is completed in the process of *nyatri*. Furthermore, the process is to take per piece the separated thread which then to be tied using raffia rope. Then it will be hoisted and woven. The semantic function of lexicon *nyepih* is separating the weaving thread that has been through the process of *nyatri*. Activities of *nyucuk* or *nyuntik* 'injecting' is the process of entering *lusi* thread to *gun* hole and to line up with the same distance. The injection process was carried out by 2 weaving workers with different tasks each. While the process of *nganiin* or to grind is the process of winding the thread onto a weaving tool named boom. This process uses mixer equipment from a number of thread that has been glazing which also depends on the fiber used. Annealing process is compiling *lusi* or *lungsi* thread based on quantity, length, and density in accordance with the structure of the cloth that will be produced.

Melut process

Source: research doc

Nyemuh (drying) process

Source: research doc

Weaving process

Source: research doc

Melut is the process of cutting raffia rope from *pakan* thread to see and make sure of the design. When the tied thread is opened or released there is still uncolored thread (white). Next the uncolored thread is to be dyed through the process of *nyatri*. The drying process (*nyemuh*) is carried out after the releasing process of tying (*melut*) and all thread is in the process of being dried by not exposing to direct sunlight. The last process from all steps is a weaving process in which the two types of thread (*lungsi* and *pakan*) are ready to be processed through the non-machine weaving tool to produce cloth weaving.

5. CONCLUSION

This research was conducted on traditional weaving in which it's applied manual technique in operating the traditional weaving tools. This non machine tools is abbreviated ATBM (*Alat Tenun Bukan Mesin*). The main materials are thread, dye, and tools weaving for furthermore processing. There are 3 types of lexicon classification found in this research which consists of material lexicon, equipment or tools lexicon, and the lexicon used in processing or workmanship. The amount of overall lexicon found is

as many as 100 lexicons. Lexicon for equipment is the most in number followed by material lexicon and lexicon in processing with the same amount. The semantic function is analyzed based on the meaning in which each lexicon has its different semantics function. The semantics function in the lexicon of materials and equipment is emphasized on the meaning because all lexicons are nouns. While the semantics function in the classification of processing lexicon is in the form of verb with the meaning and function of each lexicon.

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